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Gender and intersectional diversity structures that shape the EU Green Deal

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes

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Executive summary of recommendations

This publication presents the methodology, main findings and learning points of the secondary data analysis of the **Gender and Diversity** theme across the six SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams.

The analysis was conducted based on interview and survey data and documentation gathered during all implementation steps with experiment participants and coordinating partners. Grounded in Theories of Practice and Intersectionality, and guided by six research questions, the analysis allowed for a detailed and reflective understanding of gender in its full socio-technical dimension (i.e gender dynamics, practices & performances, gendered understandings and know-how, gendered spaces & communication), while considering its intersections with other categories that might affect inclusivity (such as age, disability etc.) in the 24 SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments (Sustainable Mobility, Biodiversity, Sustainable Food, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovation, and Clean Energy).

Key findings identified successes in the process of planning and implementing experiments in gender-sensitive ways. Examples include the creation of inclusive spaces where groups could explain their lived experiences regarding the green transition, and the early integration and consideration of gender and diversity in the planning process. In addition, the use of inclusive methods and language, and a general awareness of socially differentiated needs and experiences allowed for highlighting gendered and intergenerational ways of knowing. Observed challenges in the social experiments primarily concerned the representation of structurally vulnerable groups in governance and leadership positions as well as sociocultural and structural conditions concerning gender stereotypes and corresponding social expectations and underlying political-economic frameworks.

The following policy recommendations have been developed:

- **Acknowledge & mainstream intersectionality in EU equality strategies**

To capture diverse experiences in the green transition, existing EU equality strategies, e.g. the anti-racism action plan, the Roma, LGBTI or disability strategy, should be linked and broadened rather than separated.

- **Provide accessible & targeted training for research and project implementation**

Gender and intersectionality trainings for both researchers and implementing partners should be developed and provided in a way that is accessible and culturally responsive.

- **Adopt focused reporting, including gender indicators, in all Green Deal topics**

- **Collect holistic gender-disaggregated data on the green transition, including a focus on the impact of gender stereotypes**

Gender research on the green transition should be intensified and extended through gender-disaggregated data, including participatory research approaches, and specifically target gender stereotypes.

- **Acknowledge reproductive labour as a key pillar of the green transition**

By investigating intra-household dynamics and care, the role and complexity of unequally distributed care & household management work can reveal the invisible labour and assist appropriate consideration in transition strategies

- **Use Green Deal Communications to challenge stereotypes**

Include gender transformative approaches in Green Deal communication, especially regarding highly gendered topics like green technologies, infrastructures and related professions.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introducing the SHARED GREEN DEAL project

This report presents findings from **Cross-topic comparisons, scaling and synthesis**, building upon previous work packages of the project ‘*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*’ (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The European Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the European Union (EU) into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focused on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around **six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity**. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments (Figure 1.1) were delivered across different EU Member States and affiliated countries between April 2023 - June 2024, working with local municipalities and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) (Table A1.1¹). These are called ‘local partners’ and they carried out the social experiments autonomously, with the consortium partners providing initial training and guidance, as well as support whenever needed. Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

1 Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

Figure 1.1. Map of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments (Kovács et al., 2024)

1.2. Introducing the report

This report is based on a secondary analysis of data from the social experiments with the **main objective to identify how Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) themes cut across all six experiment streams**. The SSH themes are: (1) Gender and Diversity, (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities, (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19, (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions, (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time.

This report focuses on issues of **Gender and Diversity** and on how these were designed-in, observed and evaluated in the six experiment streams of the project. Our analysis also considers the feedback and interrelationships among the SSH priority themes as listed above. Alongside this report, four other reports were published on the respective SSH themes.

For the secondary analyses, a variety of data sources, collected within the social experiments, were considered (Table 1.2 below). Table A1.1 and Table A1.2 (in the Appendix) provide an overview of the social experiments streams and summarise the data sources in more detail, respectively.

Table 1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants	SGD consortium members (WP4)
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members

Although all data sources were reviewed, not all were equally relevant for all SSH themes. For this report, all data sources were found particularly interesting for exploring the different social cultural dimensions of gender and intersectional diversity.

1.3. Gender and Diversity

The Gender and Diversity secondary analysis aims to explore and assess the role of gender and its interactions with other issues related to structural inequalities, in shaping engagement, practical actions and outcomes within the 24 social experiments of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. The analysis is based on the understanding that gender is socially constructed, embedded in social norms, and contained in the performance of everyday life practices. Therefore, it goes beyond a binary notion of gender equality and gender representation, encompassing a wide range of societal ideas about roles, responsibilities, behaviours, social relations and power dynamics. Moreover, gender intersects and overlaps with a range of social characteristics and differences, such as age, class, racialised group, ethnicity, disability, or sexual orientation, and this influences personal and group experiences. Considering this, the analysis adopts an intersectional approach.

The following aspects summarise the ways in which we have understood, mapped and applied gender and diversity in the report:

1. Indications of **gender as a socio-cultural dimension** (including gender norms) that influence socio-cultural and behavioural change, considering gender as ‘general understandings’ of social practices (see analytical framework section 2.1 for details)
2. **Gendered practices & performances** of everyday routines, which include but are not restricted to gendered expertise, gendered interests, gendered know-how
3. Intersecting understandings and practices, which explore **how gender interacts with other categories such as age, social background, educational background or economic status**
4. **Gender balance & bias** in all aspects of the experiments, which includes aspects related to the local partners, the project partners and the experiment participants
5. **Gendered communication** in the experiment streams, which explore language and terminologies used to address issues and people
6. **Gendered dynamics**, which refer to the ways in which gender influenced interactions and relationships within the social experiments
7. **Diversity of representation, practice performance, understandings and know-how** at both the local level, and the larger European scale

2. Conceptual and methodological approach

2.1. Conceptual lenses

The Gender & Diversity Theme is informed by Theories of Practice and Intersectionality, as the main theoretical frameworks for performing the secondary analysis. This combination reflects both the preferred conceptual approach to Gender and Diversity shared by the contributing partners, as well as their experiences in performing similar analyses.

2.1.1. Theories of practice

Theories of Practice are not unified to one theory but consist of different theoretical perspectives connected by a range of “historical and conceptual similarities” (Nicolini, 2013, p.1). A unifying element of these theories is that they understand the social world as taking place in a “field of practices” (Schatzki et al., 2005 p.11).

Social practices are understood as bodily performed (Schatzki et al., 2005) and materiality mediated activities (Schatzki, 2001). Practices can refer to both sayings and doings, which are held together by different elements (Schatzki, 2002), such as: **materials** – which include ‘things, technologies, tangible physical entities and the stuff of which objects are made’, **competences**- which include “skills, know-how and technique” & **meanings**- which include “symbolic meanings, ideas and aspirations” (Shove et al., 2012, p.14). While these three elements are the simplest and most often used form of explaining practices, there are other versions, which are more relevant for this analysis. For example, Schatzki’s interpretation of practice elements, explained below, are more appropriate for adopting, to understand and contextualise gender:

practical understandings - explained as “practical sense” and “knowing how to go on” (Schatzki, 2002, pp.77-78),

rules - explained as “explicit[...] principles, precepts and instructions” (Schatzki, 2002, p. 79),

teleo-affective structure - explained as “a range of [...] projects, and tasks, [...] allied with normativized emotions and even moods” (Schatzki, 2002, p.80), and

general understandings - explained as concepts that connect wider cultural interpretations, and can include “collective concepts such as nation, state, economy or organisation, membership category such as ethnicity or gender [...]” (Welch & Warde, 2016, p. 183)

Therefore, by adopting a practice-theoretical framework for the analysis, we consider gender as socially constructed and embedded in people’s everyday practices and socio-cultural norms (Mechlenborg & Gram-Hanssen, 2020). Furthermore, following Mechlenborg and Gram-Hanssen (2020), we understand gender as ‘general understandings’ of people’s everyday practices and as meanings that can be tacit and are found to be “threading through multiple practices” (p.5). So, gender is contained, for example, in the unspoken (tacit) social norms of a specific context and practised through stereotypical everyday practices in people’s lives.

2.1.2. Intersectionality

Intersectionality as a term was coined by Crenshaw (1991), writing from her experience as a Black legal scholar in the U.S., to argue that understanding where sexism and racism overlap is vital to challenging them as systems of oppression. Since its inception, the concept has been expanded to examine how a wider range of identities intersect to inform lived realities and is now a constitutive element of mainstream feminism (Davis, 2008; Taylor, 2009). However, the uplifting of intersectionality from specific Black feminist contexts and into research projects such as this one can lead to a potential commodification and weakening of the concept, where it is sometimes used merely to list different identities without unpacking the structures underpinning them (Guidroz & Berger, 2009). With this in mind, we do not claim to systemically apply an intersectional analysis that fully unpacks all systems of domination present in the experiments and are aware of the shortcomings of our analysis in this regard. Rather, practitioners are drawn to intersectionality because they want to take a stance on a certain issue (Collins, 2015). In this case, we aim to shed light on the way that multiple issues can intersect with gender in the case of the social experiments. Our goal is to show that a mere gender analysis is not enough – and we need to strive toward intersectional understandings of gender in our research.

Further to the understandings of gender, as defined in our methodology, the concept of intersectionality can be applied in many ways, for example through exposing the structural dimensions of systems of power and how they interact. Due to constraints on both the depth and scope of the data, our use of intersectionality is mostly applied for identifying the nuances of such categories. Intersectionality can be a messy concept; the power of intersectionality is unearthing multiple and intersecting forms of structural domination, which is often highly context-dependent and do not allow for a simplistic causal analysis (Davis, 2008). Despite our best efforts to embrace such complexity, due to the nature of coding substantive amounts of data, we had to use the intersection of certain categories in order to code the data adequately. Some 'intersections' are given more attention in the analysed data than others; particularly age and disability. It is a shortcoming of this work that we have not engaged with certain intersections; in particular the racialisation embodied within categories of women, is severely lacking. However, following the coding process we have sought to move beyond the rigidity of certain identity categories as a way to neatly understand intersectionality, and instead look at the plurality and contradictions of different meanings imbued into the categories themselves.

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Research questions

RQ1. What are the dynamics of engagement regarding gender and intersectional diversity within the social experiment interactions?

RQ2. What are the gendered and intersectional ways in which people translate the concepts they will encounter in the experiment into practical action?

RQ3. In what ways are different genders engaged (or motivated) regarding the themes of the social experiments?

RQ4. How could the experiments support better gender equity and sensitivity?

RQ5. How does the Green Deal transition process impact on existing gendered practices (of each experiment)?

RQ6. In what ways, overall, do gender and diversity matter for the Green Deal transition?

The first three research questions are focused on the empirical representations of gender and intersectional diversity that were encountered in the social experiments, whereas the final three reflect our intention to be more focused and critical on inputs regarding the specific ways in which the findings can be translated into recommendations, for policy and practice. While there is a rather large number of questions, we found them to be relevant and to provide good guidance into the structuring of the coding and analysis process.

2.2.2. Data sources used and research questions they related to

This section presents the alignment of research questions which the different data sources.

Table 2.1. Research questions and data sources they relate to

Research Questions	Source
RQ1	(#DS1), (#DS2), (#DS3), (#DS4), (# DS5) and (#DS7/just for context)
RQ2	All
RQ3	All
RQ4	All
RQ5	(#DS1), (#DS2) and (#DS3)
RQ6	All

2.2.3. Gender tags and codes

The Gender and Diversity theme has used the following tags to capture data in the primary analysis of the project:

Table 2.2. Tags used to assist the primary analysis of the social experiments' interviews/ #DS1

#Gender	This tag includes mentions to gender norms, gendered interests, gendered know-how & expertise, dynamics, practices/performances
#Gender Representation	This tag includes mentions to gender representation and balance in the given context
#Intersectional	This tag includes the intersection of gender with other social characteristics, such as age, socio-cultural background, disability, education, economic situation etc.

Our main codes, developed and used through the analysis are:

1.0 Good practices	6.2 Interesectionality-Age
2.0 Problematic statements about gender	6.3 Intersectionality-Education & prof. expertise
3.0 Background & context	6.4 Intersectionality-disability
4.1 Gender norms & stereotypes	6.5 Lack of intersectionality
4.2 Gendered roles, practices & performances	6.6 Other intersectionality issues (e.g. care duties, decision-making, income, language etc.)
4.3 Gendered expertise & interests	7.1 Gender & vulnerability, justice & inequality
4.4 lack of gender issues	7.2 Gender & societal challenges post COVID
5.1 Gender representation & participation in the experiments	7.3 Gender & governance agendas, conventions & framings
5.2 Gender dynamics	7.4 Gender & geographic differences & evolutions across time
5.3 Lack of gender representation	8.0 Gendered communication & language
6.1 Interesectionality- Background	9.0 Gendered spaces

For full details and descriptions of the developed codebook please see Table A2.1 (in the Appendix).

2.2.4. Analysis Methodology

The analysis took place in 6 steps (see Tables A1.3 and A1.4, in the Appendix), including cycles of deductive, abductive and inductive analysis.

Steps 1 & 2: First, the Gender team went through the data sources and identified in what ways they contributed to responses for each research question. This was a first mapping exercise, using, deductively, our theoretical frames (practice theories and intersectionality) to perform a high level, first understanding of the data.

Step 3: The Gender team divided the data sources which were ready to be analysed (e.g. all data sources except the interview codebooks/#DS1) and performed an inductive analysis to identify codes and themes relevant to Gender & Intersectional Diversity. An initial codebook was put together and shared between the team.

Step 4: A workshop, amongst the two partners of the Gender and Diversity theme (AAU & WECF) was held, to communicate and discuss the initial coding and thematisation of the inductive analysis performed in Steps 1-3, and a final table with codes and themes was produced (see Table A2.1, in the Appendix).

Steps 5 & 6: Steps 5 & 6 started after the delivery of the codebooks (#DS1) from all social experiments as well as the final Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) data was finalised. The final data sources were added to the thematised table, and the team produced a writing plan for the deliverable report. These two steps were managed by regular online meetings amongst the Gender team, to discuss and triangulate findings. There was a change in the coding team in one of the Gender partners (WECF), with two new people joining the team halfway through Step 4. The two new team members did not have familiarity with the experiments and the SHARED GREEN DEAL project overall, so there was a period of adjustment and familiarisation with the data, combined with extensive discussion with the rest of the Gender team. When the Codebooks (#DS1) were finalised, and because of their large volume, the Gender team partly worked through them using search words and phrases in order to be time efficient. The Codebooks (#DS1) were shared amongst the Gender team, for coding purposes, and when doing so, we made sure to allocate the experiment streams according to the familiarity that the members had with each experiment.

2.2.5. Software used for the analysis of secondary data

We have used NVivo and MAXQDA programmes for performing the coding for the analysis. Since the different Gender partners do not use the same software, we shared our coded segments, by exporting them in word/excel format and then merging them to create one document. The codebooks were shared and imported in both software programs.

2.2.6. Reflexivity and collaborative analysis process

The research team comprises four researchers: three members of WECF, one of which had a smaller role in the process, and one member of AAU. Each researcher comes from a different cultural and linguistic background.

The WECF researchers are working in an NGO which is focused on the nexus of gender and intersectionality with climate and energy, therefore they are experienced with analysing issues of gender, diversity and intersectionality. They have academic backgrounds in gender studies, geography, social anthropology and environmental sciences.

The AAU researcher is experienced with qualitative analysis and with coordinating multiple data sources and perspectives into the analysis and has also been part of the primary analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, as a member of the Efficient Renovations stream. While the AAU researcher has done most of the work herself, she has had regular inputs and discussions with more senior researchers in her departments, who advised on e.g. the structure of the analysis plan, the theoretical framework and research questions of this Theme.

Continuous dialogue between the researchers and cross-evaluation of the insights we develop from the different data sources was achieved through monthly meetings, as well as workshops in which the thematisation and coding was discussed and positioned within the wider project. These interactions provided time and space for triangulation of the preliminary results and allowed us to make collective reflections on the findings, as well as the composition of the report.

Understanding the role, the perspectives and biases of the researchers that perform the analysis, is essential to better appreciate how knowledge and insights are created. The researcher team for the Gender and Diversity theme, have been only partly involved in the data collection of this project, namely through the Efficient Renovations experiment stream. Part of the Gender team (i.e three members, one of which left the team halfway through the analysis process), worked closely with the local partners of some of the renovation experiment sites, meeting monthly to discuss progress and the experience of the participants and organisers. While the Gender team members had a close insight into the experiment, they have never met with any project participants or taken part in any events of the local experiments. While conversations about gender, diversity and intersectionality were ongoing in relevance to the monthly meetings of the renovation experiment, there was never any exposure to other experiment streams in the project, through first-hand experience or in-directly through other local partners. Therefore, the Gender team's experience is based, partly, on the narratives and descriptions passed on by local partners, as well as through their immersing to the data sets available. We can say that the researchers have been partly 'insiders' in the experiments, however, in the most part, they have been external observers.

3. Understanding Gender and Intersectionality within the Social Experiments: Main findings

The SHARED GREEN DEAL project was organised around the six EU Green Deal priority topics. Each of the topic streams was implemented in four different sites across Europe, and had a specific focus group of citizens assigned, as shown in Table 3.1 below:

Table 3.1. The six streams of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and their foci on different citizen groups

Project stream/ priority topic	Target groups regarding inclusivity
Clean Energy	Intergenerational dialogue of younger (18-30) and older (65+) people
Circular Economy	Citizens with mobility and visual impairments
Efficient Renovations	Women; energy poor; families with young children (5-11)
Sustainable Mobility	Young people (11-16) in secondary education and their families
Sustainable Food	Young people (18-35) involved in food movements
Preserving Biodiversity	Those who suffered isolation during the COVID-19, especially women

The following sections present our findings which respond to the first three Research Questions, which related to the gendered dynamics in the experiments, the gendered and intersectional ways in which people translated the concepts of the experiments in practical action and the ways in which different genders engaged with the themes of these experiments.

3.1. Overview of the different experiment streams and intersections of gender with the other SSH analysis themes

3.1.1. Gender and intersectionality in the six experiments

The **Efficient Renovation and** (partly) **the Clean Energy** experiments stood out as having a more explicit consideration of gender and limited consideration of intersectional diversity, both in the design of the experiments, as well as in their facilitation and implementation. In the design stage, the Renovation stream had a target of achieving 60% women participants, while in the Energy stream, one experiment location (Poland) had a focus on developing focus groups exclusively with

women, to capture their experiences and visions for transforming their local energy infrastructure while embedding their own voices for the future of the region.

Biodiversity - There was not an explicit focus on gender from the beginning, on behalf of the project or local partners, but things came up in the gendered performances and roles, as well as in the intergenerational learning aspects.

Mobility - There were prevalent gendered stereotypes about mobility, meanings of cleanliness, femininity/ masculinity associated with cycling and driving, intersections of gender with age (children cycling to school/girls/boys), prevalence of women teachers, particularly in one of the sites (Bulgaria) and high representation of mothers in the experiment meetings, possibly as them being the main carers for children.

Circular economy - There was evidence of feminised fashion and textile industries. The project and local partners did not integrate an explicit intersectional perspective in the experiment, such as being aware of how to deal with the gendered industries or prevailing stereotypes. The main insights are that gender was treated as an issue of representation of women/men in the experiments and the engagement with disability was done implicitly or indirectly through organisations who work with people with a disability, instead of involving them directly.

The Sustainable Food stream did not integrate an explicit intersectional perspective in the experiments; they had implicit ideas of how to engage children and young people into the experiment. Some insights were gained in regard to canteen work as a feminised labour and its connection to economic precarity and education (non-native speaking) and to the notion of sustainable food transition being observed as of having more interest by women, especially regarding organic farming, while farming as such is a men-dominated industry.

3.1.2. Intersections between SSH themes

Further to the insights above about how gender and intersectional diversity were encountered in the social experiments, there were also insights about how the other themes of the secondary analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project intersected and were presented in our analysis.

In the following section, we explore how Gender and Intersectional Diversity are discussed in relation to the other four SSH priority themes: (1) Gender and Diversity, (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities, (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19, (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions, (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time.

Due to structural inequalities present across different societies, e.g. in regard to unpaid care work and low-paid labour, the **Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities** theme (Bharucha, 2025, in this collection) has the biggest overlap with gender. Those intersections concern challenges in target group engagement as well as structural disadvantages and vulnerabilities of participants. Specifically, intersectional disadvantage between socio-economic factors, racialisation and gender and the consequences of such disadvantages, were mentioned in the data connected to housing conditions and energy poverty (e.g. in the Efficient Renovation stream), household structure, financial situation and intersections with race (e.g. in the Circular Economy stream), trust towards the project (e.g. in the Preserving Biodiversity stream) or employment, old-age-provision and health (e.g. in the Clean Energy stream). The role of gender in the **Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19 theme** (Truninger et al., 2025, in this collection) concerns a broad range of issues, such as social isolation. It was, for example, mentioned as a co/relation between gender and mental health issues of people and difficulty in circumstances with the need for social support such as pregnancy and birth. The intersection of gender with **Governance Agendas, Conventions and Framings** (Gray et al., 2025, in this collection) is reflected in the Clean Energy and Sustainable Mobility stream, primarily through

mentions of political participation of women in different levels of decision-making. A reflection of different levels of political responsibility and the inclusion of women in decision-making can be observed in encouraging conscious behaviour and empowerment on individual level, linking women's political participation to a community-focused style of governance and based on daily lived experiences. The Sustainable Mobility Stream had strong reflections on the importance of raising awareness for gendered perspectives and experiences in the political realm. Finally, gender in relation to the SSH priority theme **Geographic differences and evolutions across time** (Nieboer et al., 2025, in this collection) is mostly linked to structural and socio-economic conditions and roles, e.g. women's increasing role in small-scale farming and sustainable agriculture practices (e.g. in the Sustainable Food stream) as well as in socially transmitted knowledge (e.g. in the Preserving Biodiversity stream). A prominent theme in the Clean Energy stream were some women participants' insecurities about their future in the region and the need for local structural changes.

3.2. Dynamics of engagement regarding gender and intersectionality

Box 3.2a summarises the most prevalent representations of gender dynamics across the different social experiments.

Box 3.2a. The gender dynamics observed in the social experiments

1. **Unequal Participation Despite Representation:** Gender balance in attendance was widely reported, however this did not always ensure active participation, as there were gendered differences in the ways people engaged depending on the topic discussed.
2. **Structural Barriers Limited Inclusive Engagement:** Intersecting structural factors, such as caring, time poverty, and job precarity, shaped who could participate and how, yet misframed as 'vulnerabilities'.
3. **Inconsistent Application of Intersectionality:** Efforts to include diverse participants addressed intersecting identities unevenly, with more attention paid to age and disability due to the project design, and less attention paid to racial and ethnic dynamics except in isolated cases like the Roma community.
4. **Gendered and Generational Learning:** Gendered experiences and intergenerational knowledge-sharing played a key role in translating Green Deal concepts into practical actions, especially through women's engagement in families and schools.
5. **Gendered Roles and Expertise:** Women's participation in feminised sectors and caring roles shaped sustainable practices, while gendered divisions influenced access to technical knowledge and decision-making.
6. **Gendered Stereotypes and Practices:** Persistent gender stereotypes affected how expertise and roles were perceived, with women often undervalued in technical fields but also bringing unique approaches to sustainability challenges.
7. **Gendered Power Dynamics and Division of Labour Persist:** Traditional gender roles and power imbalances often result in men occupying visible leadership positions while women hold informal influence and bear disproportionate unpaid care work.

3.2.1. Characteristics of gender representation within the experiments

Whilst our analysis plan presents gender as general understandings, which are socially constructed and reproduced through social norms and everyday interactions, the data we are working with often characterises gender as a category. The category of ‘women’ comes up repeatedly as a site where meaning is made. According to Lorber (1993), the social construction of categories is what makes them appear normal, or fixed – when in reality they are dynamic and fluid. We can see that many meanings are imbued into the category of ‘women’ within the research findings.

This categorisation of gender, using the binary of men-women, e.g. talking about gender representation, has been a way for social experiment participants and local partners to make sense of gender in the social experiments. It has become evident that the socio-cultural and performative dimensions of gender (i.e. gendered performances, gendered dynamics, gendered spaces etc, as explained in Section 1.3), have not been thoroughly considered or appreciated by all partners involved, and therefore their reporting has been more limited.

For example, reporting how many women and men were in the room, what the women were talking about, or how women felt about the social experiments, was a way to easily categorise and understand gender. Our aim here is twofold; to present and reflect on both these categorisations reported in the experiment data, as well as to provide a critical lens for reviewing and evaluating these insights.

In terms of access to the social experiments, the idea of gendered representation was often a binary construction of ‘men and women’. The idea that the experiments were gender balanced in their representation comes up repeatedly (e.g. Efficient Renovations, Ireland, #DS1; Biodiversity, Ireland, #DS1; Clean Energy, UK #DS1; Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, #DS3; Clean Energy, Poland, #DS5). In some cases, there was reflection across the experiment streams on the gendered ways in which representation would be difficult to achieve, relating to the fact that women had care responsibilities. There were a few instances in which the local partners stated that they took into account such responsibilities for the timing (e.g. meetings) of the social experiments, so that they were organised at times women did not have care responsibilities and thus could participate (e.g. Clean Energy, Poland, #DS3; Efficient Renovation, Spain #DS3). Additionally, the Efficient Renovation stream acknowledged the time burden of women and stated they needed to do extra work to make the process easier for women to participate so as not to add to this time burden (Efficient Renovation, Spain, #DS3). This care issue also intersected with age, as there were some examples of younger women dropping out of the social experiments due to having more care responsibilities (Biodiversity, Ireland, #DS3).

The vulnerabilities framing comes up repeatedly and highlights how hard-to-reach groups were conceptualised more broadly throughout the social experiments. For example, there is repeated discussion within the Efficient Renovations stream of women being overrepresented in more vulnerable positions or groups. This was also linked to structural issues:

“OK, let’s see, when I think of vulnerable people, I also think that there is a high percentage of women. Well, because it has been shown that they have worse contracts, temporary contracts or contracts with fewer hours, that sometimes they have family responsibilities.”

[Efficient Renovation, Spain, participant, social worker, 37yo, woman², #DS1]

2 When collecting data on participants’ genders, they were asked to self-identify. We report genders using the terms “man”, “woman” and “non-binary”, in accordance with World Health Organisation guidance on sex and gender terminology. See: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>

When it comes to housing, the vulnerabilities framing hinders transformative potential because it puts the onus on groups themselves rather than the structure they are part of (Wolferink, 2021). However, as the above quote demonstrates, there are instances where the social structures are accounted for by participants. This indicates an understanding of structural issues and their gendered impact. Other participants in the Efficient Renovation Stream indicated that women were over-represented in this social experiment (despite the experiment focus on achieving 60% women representation), in particular coming from vulnerable backgrounds: “I would say that most of the neighbours... who came in a vulnerable situation were female.” [Efficient Renovation, Spain, participant, 84yo, man, #DS1] and “Especially if we look at vulnerable households, in general there was more female participation.” [Efficient Renovation, Spain, participant, social worker, 37yo, woman, #DS1]. These quotes highlight the complexity of the position of women’s representation within the Efficient Renovation stream, acknowledged as being in more vulnerable positions. Whilst this framing is not ideal, it is the way the participants make sense of women in precarious positions.

In the case of disabilities within the Circular Economy stream, the lack of structural analysis combined with the vulnerabilities framing led to disabled people being not properly represented within the experiment:

“Vulnerable target groups such as association of people with disabilities and visually impaired were contacted and informed about the project, nevertheless their capacity and relevancy to the project’s objectives were such that did not allow them to join the experiment actively.”

[Circular Economy, Cyprus, local partner, #DS4]

The understanding of disabled people’s ‘capacity’ to engage in the project objectives implies that disabled people have limited capacity to engage in certain everyday practices that people without disabilities can engage in. Instead, the onus should be put on structures that make the world less accessible for people with disabilities, rather than the capacities of disabled individuals. In Slovenia, an overt awareness of the potential power imbalance between the project organisers and disabled groups also hindered participation:

“The disabled groups were mostly engaged through social organisations that were participating at the experiment. The challenges were that we didn’t want to force disabled people to participate at the workshops themselves but through their representatives (organisations). We understand that this kind of approach is respectful toward disabled people.” [Circular economy, Slovenia, local partner, #DS4]

The idea that you would be ‘forcing’ disabled people to engage in the project also implies that these people might not have the capacity or agency to decide for themselves. Whilst there was some acknowledgement of different technologies required for those who have accessibility needs [e.g. Circular Economy, France, #DS5, Circular Economy, France, #DS1], as well as the accessibility of meeting spaces more broadly [Circular Economy, France, #DS1], this failure to engage disabled groups directly only serves to reinforce their positioning as a ‘hard to reach’ group.

The gendered nature of the sectors participating in the social experiments also affected and shaped the dynamics of engagement. For example, the textile sector is mentioned as being feminised in the Circular Economy stream [Circular Economy, Slovenia, #DS1]. Additionally, the canteen workers in the Sustainable Food stream in Slovakia were described as a low status job mainly made up of women [Sustainable Food, Slovakia, #DS1]. This also intersected with language barriers, as some of these women were immigrants and unable to participate in the experiment as they did not speak Slovakian. This shows a shortcoming in reaching people who fall into intersecting categories of exclusion; being working class women in a feminised low paid sector who do not speak the local language. Finally, in the Efficient Renovation stream, the male dominated building construction industry was evident through the interview data with examples of people suggesting that “usually

in Vilnius or in Lithuania, the builder is naturally a man, and they are the ones who are doing all the work, and the woman is working behind the closed doors” [Efficient Renovation, Lithuania, participant, 65yo, man, #DS1], as well as reports from women in the building industry who “*have experienced a certain difficulty as a female architect in front of fellow male architects.*” [Efficient Renovation, Hungary, participant, architect, 37yo, woman, #DS1]. These examples highlight that stereotypical professional roles are being reproduced in the specific locations, and in turn shape people’s expectations in regard to both the trusted expertise, as well as the experience and familiarity with these sectors.

3.2.2. Intersectional challenges of participation and interaction in the social experiments

In order to understand the dynamics of engagement regarding gender and intersectional diversity within the social experiment interactions, both equality of access and equality of participation should be examined. Equality of access concerns how people were represented and able to participate in the social experiments from the beginning, but it does not necessarily mean equality of participation.

Box 3.2b. Equality of participation

Equality of participation concerns the dynamics that arise throughout the social experiments, and the ways in which people are restricted or enabled to participate once in that space. Just because you have managed to get a diverse group of people into a space, does not mean everyone in that space gets to participate equally. Despite the widely reported gender balance, this did not always translate into equal discussion space.

“Women had a harder time speaking because some men talked a lot and liked to hear themselves talk, which often derailed the discussion”

[Sustainable Food, Italy, participant, 34yo woman, #DS1]

As the quote above suggests, there was several instances of men talking more than women , although it should be noted there was also a couple of instances of women being quite vocal, such as women representing single households [Efficient Renovation, Hungary, participant, youth professional, 43yo, woman, #DS1].

“During discussions, there were subgroups, and in my opinion, we need more trained people to moderate these subgroups. Talking with participants from groups managed by my colleagues, who had never done it before, revealed some difficulties, especially for the women, because the men talked too much, and the other moderators couldn’t manage to quiet them, give space, or ask for everyone’s opinion.” [Sustainable Food, Slovakia, participant- business partner in company dealing with farming, 26yo, man, #DS1]

Although the need for a trained moderator was not always expressed, the idea that women were not given enough space by men came up in multiple other instances [e.g. Sustainable Food, Italy, #DS1; Efficient Renovation, Spain, #DS1]. This also depended on the topics being discussed – with a few mentions of women being less comfortable to ask questions or talk about ‘technical topics’, indicating the impact of gendered stereotypes in relation to STEM topics [Clean Energy, Spain, participant, energy

facilitator, 46yo, woman; Efficient Renovation, Hungary, participant, renewable energy professional, 24yo, woman #DS1].

The dynamics of participation were also obscured by a lack of understanding or misinterpretation, on behalf of local partners, as to how gender could be understood within the experiments. There was repeated reporting, for example, through the monthly field notes (#DS3), that gender dynamics were not observed or not present [e.g. Biodiversity, Ireland #DS3; Clean Energy, Spain, #DS3], which most probably points to a lack of understanding of how local partners could record or communicate issues of gender, rather than a lack of dynamics themselves. For example:

“Gender issues were not an issue to anyone. No gender dynamics were seen by [male person]. The group as a whole, came happier as a group, (he) couldn’t say that there were gender dynamics. The group was very balanced between gender; he sees it a very positive thing. It was beneficial to have such a mixed group.” [Biodiversity, Sweden, local partner, #DS2].

It is also noteworthy that in this instance the lack of gender dynamics observed is linked with the group being happy, and the gender balance is inferred as being a reason for the lack of gender issues. This perhaps points to a lack of awareness on how to observe gendered interactions as opposed to their absence. Further to this, there might have been other reasons which prevented local partners from recording gender and diversity issues, such as lack of time, uncertainty of linguistic communication in which to express such issues, as well as, perhaps not enough persistence from the project partners who followed the experiment, in regard to enquiring about gender issues in general. One example of how these dynamics could have been observed and recorded is a discussion of family and parents, which came up a lot, particularly in the Sustainable Mobility, Biodiversity and Sustainable Food streams, in instances where they worked with children and schools. A heterosexual family unit can obscure a lot of gender dynamics in spaces such as the household, and so when participants or local partners spoke of parents and families, making decisions on topics related to the experiment (e.g., driving for mobility, sustainable food choices or home renovation decisions), it was not always possible or clear to understand the internal, potentially gendered dynamics and roles. This lack of nuance in terms of how decisions in the family are taken, makes it harder to unpack gendered dynamics, as these are also implicated in local social norms, roles and everyday practices.

Whilst there was emphasis on having people from ‘diverse backgrounds’ in the experiments [e.g. Sustainable Food, The Netherlands, local partner, #DS3], what makes these backgrounds diverse was less clear. On the other hand, age repeatedly came up as a category that was focused on, in terms of representation. Age was an easy way for experiment participants to explain intersectional diversity by highlighting challenges such as an *“issue with giving enough space to women, especially young women, but not only them.”* [Sustainable Food, Italy, participant, 66yo, man, #DS1] or opportunities, such as *“what made me happy was actually the young women farmers, that like in this generation there are people who want to do this and are passionate about it.”* [Sustainable Food, Slovakia, participant, 26yo, man, #DS1].

Discussion of ethnic minorities and racialised groups was significantly less prevalent. For example, there was no systemic attention paid to how racialisation may intersect with other focus categories in the social experiments (e.g., gender, age, disability). There was some discussion of how people from different cultural backgrounds can affect knowledge-making, e.g. in relation to food [e.g. Sustainable Food, Netherlands, #DS1, #DS4]. Engagement of different ethnicities comes up across the streams [Biodiversity, Greece, #DS1; Biodiversity, Ireland, #DS1; Sustainable Mobility, Portugal, #DS1; Sustainable Food, Netherlands, #DS1], but it was not conducted systematically and therefore shows a gap in terms of engaging with racialised groups. Engaging Roma communities came up in the Efficient Renovation experiment. As a systemically discriminated group of people in Hungary, it was important to design an inclusive approach and recruitment of members of this community. The local partner put in place a worker, in the local area, who the Roma community respected (and was also of Roma origin), and that made a positive difference in both the recruitment to the experiment as well as in the implementation

and the building of trust. However, statements from the experiment participants, in the Efficient Renovation stream, suggest that Roma people still feel excluded or find it challenging to successfully access initiatives that might exist at local or national level. This shows that whilst engaging respected community members is vital to building trust and establishing a good relationship with excluded racial minorities, such trust is not a panacea to the systemic exclusion and discrimination these groups have faced for hundreds of years.

3.3. Gendered and intersectional ways of translating Green Deal concepts into practical action

Since the experiments did not necessarily follow participants' implementation of the practices related to the experiments' foci, and also due to their short duration, it is not possible to give conclusive insights into how exactly people translated the social experiment experiences and learnings into action. However, we can highlight some of the learnings regarding the concepts, or more precisely the topics of the experiments, that do have a gender component to them and in some cases allowed for a broadening of perspectives around the concepts tackled. The following three sections (3.3.1 to 3.3.3) present some insights, initially from our research question 5, relating to, how the Green Deal transition process impact on existing learning practices of each experiment, combined with findings relating to research questions 2 and 3, which explore the gendered and intersectional ways that people translate concepts of the social experiments into action and the ways that different genders are engaged or motivated regarding the themes of the social experiments.

3.3.1. Gendered and generational learning

Sharing experiences that are uniquely undergone by girls cycling to school led to the topic being made visible to adults – parents, teachers and local politicians. What was perceived as 'unimaginable', namely girls experiencing sexual harassment on their way to school in their uniforms, opened up a debate about the gendered circumstances and risks of the everyday act of riding your bike and gave space to gendered learning. It made the knowledge that only girls hold, accessible and extended their chance of sharing other reasons and norms why they avoid using their bike as a mobility option to get to school. They explained stereotypes and gender norms, such as being teased for the way this physical activity can make you sweat or have messy hair and clothes, while

"(...) boys are expected to look kind of mucky. You know, culturally we don't mind it so much when they're sweaty and smelly. But girls are supposed to be pristine, (...)"

[Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, participant, garden designer, 45yo, woman, #DS1]

Box 3.3. Gendered intergenerational knowledge-transfer

The overall notion of long-term learning from what has been experienced and discussed in the experiments, especially in the Biodiversity stream, hints to evidence that knowledge transfer between different generations, happens frequently along gender lines, e.g. passing down local ecosystem knowledge between mothers and daughters, e.g. participants suggesting that *“my mother, when she was alive, when we went to a place where she was in nature, she knew how to distinguish some trees, some plants, some flowers (...) she knew how to distinguish because obviously my grandmother, who didn’t grow up in Athens, taught her, (...)”* [Preserving Biodiversity, Greece, participant, not in work, 55yo, woman, #DS1]

Or in other cases, the passing down of local land knowledge between women in the same family:

“(...) sitting down (...) with my mother, (...) to talk about the different placenames and the area names and how they all relate back to animals, creatures and sort of landscape type (...). (...) it drew out other stories about land uses and how that used to be done back in the 50s and 60s in Ireland [farming practices],” [Preserving Biodiversity, Ireland, participant, teacher, 35yo, woman, #DS1].

Additional action on learnings was generated by the fact that many parents, mothers in particular, participated in the experiments and shared their experiences with their close and extended family, in some cases leading to change of practices. This was also especially evident in the Biodiversity stream, where women teachers took the chance to translate their learnings for their kindergarten or school children. Vice versa it was also remarked that children have had an influence on their parents e.g. regarding their spending and mobility practices.

3.3.2. Gendered roles influencing interests

As pointed out previously, especially in areas of work that are socially feminised, such as the textile and food sector, women in our experiments are reporting that their practices in relation to production and consumption are changing into a more sustainable, circular way. They are e.g., sharing clothes:

“(...) you no longer need the latest shirt, you already bought it in a better quality (...). We’ll lend each other pretty pieces, you get pretty things from your mom, even you tell yourself, ‘wait, I’m going to buy something better because, maybe, I could lend it to my daughter’. And so, all at once, you are no longer in the impulse fashion purchase(...)” [Circular Economy, France, participant, business owner, 42yo, woman, #DS1].

More broadly, addressing schools as a projection of a space where gendered roles and jobs are enacted and reproduced, producing food for school canteens is perceived as an unattractive *“topic for farmers as this is still seen as a woman’s job”*, and as a low-skilled, low-paid job with limited career progression [Sustainable Food, Slovakia, local partner, #DS3]. Although mobility is itself not a women-dominated sector, in the experiments, as they were connected to schools, women were highly overrepresented as school teachers, and mothers were the responsible parent to contact for experiment issues (e.g. frequently seen in Bulgaria), demonstrating their engagement with the topic in a more active way, due to their role as primary carers.

In realms that are traditionally masculinised fields of work, e.g. energy and construction, the experiments engaging in the clean energy transition, seem to have changed the awareness of some

participants towards upcoming opportunities for social changes, e.g. on labour market, but also on political engagement and level of power for all genders and young people. While at the same time home renovation was discussed in the light of traditional assumptions of “*women looked after what was inside, and men looked after what was outside*” [e.g. Efficient Renovations, Ireland, #DS3], hinting to structures of decision-making and household labour distribution that are often invisible to outsiders. In relation to energy-efficiency improvements and the interaction with the relevant contractors it was reported that “*(...) women are more interested in the comfort of the home and therefore tend to look for improvements, whether that be insulation or improved heating systems.*” [Efficient Renovations, Ireland, local partner, #DS3] while they “*also seem to be more aware of energy efficiency aspects and they are the ones who watch energy consumption at home.*” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, participant, shop assistant, 43yo, woman, #DS1]. The latter statement relates to women managing the energy consumption by controlling how many or what energy intensive appliances they use, rather than monitoring energy consumption through smart meters and apps.

3.3.3. Gender stereotypes and their relation to practice, performances, and expertise

Most experiments focused on matters which involve different stereotypical gendered practices and performances with participants mirroring social stereotypes on gendered interests and expertise. In the Efficient Renovation and Clean Energy streams for example, the argument that women are more interested or close to the interior of their home, e.g. suggesting which kinds of improvements they want, while men are more focused on the outside and e.g. the greater technical processes behind renovation measures or new renewable energy techniques, as the quote suggests:

“I think it is very important, although more and more women work outside or we can share tasks at home, but I think it is still very important or more relevant the role of women in this sense.”
[Clean Energy, Spain, participant, teacher, 48yo, woman, #DS1]

Regarding the professional realm on the one hand, a questioning or mistrust of skills and knowledge assembled through formal education, is observed in relation to women architects and building professionals:

“There are many times when we go out, it’s not my job to communicate with them [people living in houses that are renovated; the interviewee is referring to them being from a specific social class], it’s my female colleague’s job, but then they come looking for me because they think that surely a man is going to decide.” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, participant, project manager, 52yo, man, #DS1]

On the other hand, some participants generally see it more ‘normal’ that men would attend meetings where expertise is exchanged as they are believed to inherently be “*measuring [it] with their eyes.*” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, participant, shop assistant, 43yo, woman, #DS1] in regard to, e.g. construction related topics. The data suggest an acknowledgement that times have changed regarding the traditional expectations on women and men, but it is still surprising that women come into these spaces of expertise and share their knowledge. This points to underlying stereotypes, expectations and norms that are socially constructed, learnt and shared by all of us, and that take time and effort to unlearn or change.

However, there is even more to learn from some examples that observed gendered practices and knowledge generation. To stay in the realm of professional expertise in construction jobs, the local partner in Spain has recognised that in times of fluctuations in material prices, architects chose

different ways to respond to it. For example, a man architect wanted to keep the prices as agreed upon, negatively affecting the constructor, while another architect, this time a woman, aimed at establishing consensus that serves everyone. Without over-emphasising this example or generalising it towards gendered practices, it can be said that the observation of gender-specific differences in how practices are performed can lead to more nuanced information about gendered dynamics and their origins. It is further possible with such an observation to reflect on the historical events and societal structures that led to diverse social learnings and formed different roles and attached expectations.

3.4. Gendered engagement with green deal topics

One of the recurring statements in the data, on reported gendered dynamics of the experiments, is that there were no perceived differences between men and women, and that every participant was treated equally and no discrimination took place, because all were united by the same goals towards the transition topics.

When encountering differences in the dynamics of engagement in some cases, it was argued that differences were attributed to personality or national identity rather than gender.

While being aware that the groups of the social experiments have been rather small and possibly more united and open towards each other than larger and looser societal groups, gendered dynamics are present in the societal structure we operate in every day due to power dynamics shaped by patriarchy, colonialism, capitalism among others. Being aware that local partners had to pay attention to various foci or analysis points that the SHARED GREEN DEAL project set for them in the limited period of 12 months, we aim to jointly reflect on some of these structures here. We focus on different interests from participants toward the topics that were reported in the data, therefore answering our research question 3. We also address the lack of reflection on why different genders show different interests, strengths or confidence regarding the themes of the social experiments.

3.4.1. Gendered norms influencing engagement and roles

What topics different genders are engaged or interested in, stand in context of how they are shaped by social norms in their up-bringing and social and cultural interactions. To be more specific, it stands in connection with what they were taught by others or their past life experiences. In the Clean Energy transition in Bełchatów, Poland, for example, women are described to be:

“(...) neglected on multiple levels. That’s also a big reason why these women are not entrepreneurial, they simply do not believe in themselves. They were brought up to be heavenly mothers, to be the Lord’s handmaidens.” [Clean Energy, Poland, participant, pensioner, 62yo, woman, #DS1]

This statement reflects prevalent stereotypes and local experiences and suggests that there has been a negative feeling amongst women themselves about their ability to break through established roles and societal expectations.

Furthermore, the differences in transport modes chosen, as discussed in section 3.3.1, suggest that boys in school showed more interest in cars and bikes than girls and were eager to learn more about sustainable transportation topics. When it comes to public transport it was reported that there seems to be a “*male-female divide on the confidence levels of using public transportation*” [Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, local participant, garden designer, 45yo, woman, #DS1],

acknowledging that e.g. most bus drivers are men, who tend to be unfriendly and stressed, which can pose a uncomfortable situation for young, teenage girls. This statement again reflects prevalent social stereotypes on professions, which could be challenged by younger generations, however, they currently seem to be reproduced by them.

One of the main gendered roles that was evident in the data, was the management of tasks, finances and household members at home, and the multi-tasking of these responsibilities attributed mostly to women, as the quote below suggests:

“Yes, women are more available, they tend to have young children, so they’re at home, and they can deal with these things better and faster than men, who may even be away at a workers’ hostel, so they’re not at home very much during the week.” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, participant, renewable energy professional, 24yo, woman, #DS1]

The analysis shows that women are more engaged and vocal in groups when it comes to the concept of transition, affecting their everyday experiences and *“daily life economics,”* [Clean Energy, Spain, local partner, #DS3]. The attention and responsibility of women for issues such as energy bills was highlighted as their dedicated task in rural areas, whereas in urban areas heterosexual couples are more likely to distribute this task between themselves. However, women’s overall depiction as ‘household managers’ stands in close connection to women being the primary carers of children, older people, relatives with health issues or disabilities or other unpaid care work activities, while, in some or most contexts women additionally engage in paid (full or part-time) labour.

These care work responsibilities shape women’s entanglement with the SHARED GREEN DEAL topics in their everyday life. Women, who reported to be the primary care takers at home, often need to adapt their daily routines to take children to potentially different schools and out-of-school activities. Additionally, some women are limited in e.g. participating in the experiments because of their children’s needs or because of family members’ expectations, such as:

“We had two adults on the team who had experienced social isolation, particularly during (...) COVID-(...) Both are women. One described her need for constant socializing and that the study circle was a great experience of this (...). She had to face her children’s opposition to participating in the study circles and therefore missed some of the meetings.” [Preserving Biodiversity, Greece, local partner, #DS2]

At the same time, a change to their daily routines, such as renovation activities taking place at home, poses immediate consequences or challenges to the everyday practices of women as carers or household managers:

“Well, the expenses, the kids, raising the kids, having to renovate, having to cram into one room because the other two were being done, or they were being extended. We were talking about the day-to-day hardships, basically.” [Efficient Renovation, Hungary, participant, renewable energy professional, 24yo, woman, #DS1]

The issue of limited space is accompanied by the responsibility for family comfort challenged by potential restrictions to cook warm food or wash and dry clothes, whilst coordinating renovation professionals etc. These issues are adding new layers of mental load to their lives. [e.g. Efficient Renovation, Spain, participant, retired, 69yo, man, #DS1]

In addition, through the interviews, it turns out that most interviewees seem to be in heterosexual, long-term relationships, where certain practices and/or sharing of tasks have evolved alongside stereotypical societal roles but are not considered unequal or overburdening on one side.

“The impression I got (...) was that she did a lot of the background work (...) when it came to discussion with contractors, her husband did that. Women do the fact finding, but then men

do things like delivery greetings etc. It is a shared endeavour. But if it's inside the house it is the woman who will offer the cup of tea, or whatever. It is a balance. I wouldn't say there is an overburdening of one side.” [Efficient Renovations, Ireland, #DS3].

One of the main recurring arguments by women regarding technical questions in the Clean Energy and Efficient Renovation experiments is that their husbands just have a better eye and more knowledge, leaving no reason for them to get involved. This presents a good example of how social expectations of the division of labour and interests can be reproduced in heterosexual relationships.

3.4.2. Women's roles and representation in sustainability transitions

Almost all experiments intended to engage local community leaders to connect to e.g., women in the community (e.g. Clean Energy, Poland), young people (e.g. Circular Economy, UK) or neighborhood members (e.g. Efficient Renovation, Spain) in the experiments. Especially, in the Clean Energy experiment that took place in Poland, the potential of women as leaders of their community and local energy transition was highlighted as a positive and encouraging development enabled through the social experiment. Furthermore, in some experiments, such as the Sustainable Food and Efficient Renovation, it was predominantly women that were leading the community action, such as organising and running eco-home tours (e.g. in Efficient Renovation, Ireland) and being the representative of the local partner who connected the community.

There is further evidence in the experiments, as well as in the participation in the final interviews, that the overall proportion of women among the active members of transition initiatives is much higher than men, and also that women, overall, show a high interest in environmental issues as well as for living sustainable lives (e.g. in the Circular Economy; Biodiversity; Circular Economy). There is evidence in the data which suggests that this higher interest in environmental issues or higher participation in the commons, might be learnt through social upbringing within families and communities, learning by seeing and doing, as the quote below exemplifies:

“(...) my mother also taught me to recycle, to use public transport. So, whatever I do – I mean recycling, using public transport – I got it all from her. (...). For example, if we use the stove we cook on, we don't turn on the other stove in the winter. Or the dryer so we don't waste electricity.” [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, participant, student, 10yo, girl]

On the other hand, we want to highlight that the role of women in regard to the notion of care is often falsely understood as an inherent, biological trait. It is important to observe that the quote below is given by a woman, therefore showcasing how this notion of primary care responsibility has been nurtured or reinforced through multiple generations:

“(...) because women look at the world a bit differently, as they are biologically inclined to create good, nice conditions to live in, work, give birth, and bring up children. They genuinely care. You could really feel how much they care about the city developing in the right direction, creating prospects and offering interesting alternatives.” [Clean Energy, Poland, participant, energy policy representative, 50yo, woman, #DS1]

Furthermore, our analysis revealed the gendered space of leadership, in the community and at home. For example, in the Efficient Renovation stream, men were often presented as those responsible for technical or financial decision regarding renovation, confidently speaking about the given topic, while women took a step back in the experiment interactions. However, as the quote below

exemplifies, women might have more control or impact in the household decision making process, even if not publicly shown:

“Okay, maybe there was this one loudmouth young man who came in for the first time. He had a very big mouth and everything, but I saw that the woman was the boss. I mean, what the woman comes up with, she cleverly projects onto the man, that’s how we women are, you know – You wear the pants, but I control you from behind. That was quite obvious there.” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, participant, community youth professional, 43yo, yo, woman, #DS1]

This perspective cannot be generalised as such, however these assumptions stand in direct connection to the notion that women are considered in several experiment settings as having direct influence on family and community level, *“(…) educating women can serve to educate the offspring, to educate the elders, to change consumption habits in households.”* [Clean Energy, Spain, participant, university teacher, 48yo, yo, woman, #DS1]. As established above, care work is distributed unequally in our societies and in our data from the social experiments, leading to women being the primary carers, carrying the double burden of unpaid care work, being responsible for the well-being of their family members, and paid labour. This socially embedded and learnt care expectations and duties translate to wider societal structures, such as generational responsibility for a livable planet and sustainability transitions, healthy food, a home adequately equipped for the family needs, among others.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

4.1. How the social experiments supported better gender equity and sensitivity

The following sections relate to our research questions 4 and 6, which refer to ways in which the experiments can support better gender equity and sensitivity, as well as showcase the different ways in which gender and intersectional diversity matter for the Green Deal transition. To compose these, we provide some learning points from the six social experiment streams, spread into two categories: 1. Successful learning points and 2. Problematic areas that need to be addressed

4.1.1. Successful learning points from the design and implementation of the social experiments regarding Gender and Intersectional Diversity

1. Gender and intersectional diversity need to be considered at an early stage of planning an experiment. Actions such as “*considering the age and gender of participants to support generational and gender inclusivity.*” [Sustainable Food, Italy, local partner, #DS6], and “*use the experience of [...] colleagues of the gender equality department and social services department.*” [Clean Energy, Spain, local partner, #DS6] are good practices that need to be discussed and allocated as a responsibility to those who will recruit members of the community.
2. Inclusive and gender-sensitive language are important for all communication methods. This includes the use of local languages or dialects, as well as non-verbal notions which might be gendered or excluding, to ensure that participants are comfortable in the planned interactions and in all material relating to the experiment.
3. Generating safe spaces for allowing multiple perspectives to be heard [Efficient Renovation, Lithuania, local partner, #DS4] is important for enabling a diverse environment for interaction. This includes making space for all genders to enter and participate in currently gendered domains, such as agriculture or building construction.
4. Creating “*transparent processes where the reasons for the decisions taken are known.*” [Clean Energy, Spain, local partner #DS6] is vital for all members of social experiments, as well as others external or adjacent to it.
5. Inclusive and gender-appropriate planning for the practical implementation of the experiment interactions is important, in regard to transportation, accommodation, care provision etc., allowing participants to have support in issues such as accessing a venue, providing care for children or other dependants, accommodating specific needs etc.
6. The social experiments encouraged and supported inclusive learning processes and methods, such as using video media to reach isolated adults, as this had become normalised during the Pandemic. It is important that reaching not just for consensus but trying to understand the experiences of those that might be sidelined or sitting outside what might be considered the ‘norm’ or average in a society.
7. Assess who could be considered socially excluded or disadvantaged, in a given context, and focus on how to support their inclusion. Some examples include highlighting the experience of women, girls, disabled people or other groups which might be under-represented or in challenging situations, such as done in the Sustainable Mobility stream [Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, local partner, #DS4].

4.1.2. Problematic areas highlighted in the data regarding Gender and Intersectional Diversity

1. Governance and leadership of the organisations involved, as well as of the structure of a social experiment did not necessarily involve a diverse range of stakeholders, such as individuals and groups of people that might face challenging situations, such as energy poverty, or people with disabilities. Some of the experiments considered local diversity standards, such as “*principles written in the Portuguese Diversity Charter (...) which commit to diversity as an ethical imperative.*” [Circular economy, Portugal, local partner, #DS6]. However, the definition and inclusion of people in vulnerable situations in practice, is often difficult and context specific. Understanding the structural factors that shape exclusion and put people in vulnerable situations in each context is essential to design in the strategy for an appropriate engagement. In the future, there should be more comprehensive training for those involved in similar initiatives, on how to conceptualise hard-to-reach groups so as not to reify their precarity.
2. Several social expectations around Europe, despite the different socio-cultural contexts, continue to put pressure on women, such as assigning them the role of the primary carer or household manager, or assuming their time availability because they are home. Such examples reveal prevalent gender stereotypes, which can prevent a more inclusive approach as they reproduce assumptions about gendered roles and practices that allow women’s household labour to become invisible, taken for granted and even undervalued.
3. Women are disproportionately affected by social inequalities such as poverty, lower formal education and/or professional qualifications, and often found ‘trapped’ in low paid jobs and positions. This can be misinterpreted as a lack of ambition or interest to change, as exemplified in the Sustainable Food experiment: “*(...) kitchen chefs, they are all female, low-paid, have no willingness to learn or do differently because they lack motivation due to low salaries, hard work, no career progression.*” [Sustainable Food, country, local partner, #DS3]. There is a need for an analysis of the structural causes of these inequality dynamics, taking into account the reproductive, unpaid labour that is to a high extent performed by women, and which sustains our societies and its reproduction beyond the capitalistic market.
4. The process of understanding, communicating and logging gender and intersectional diversity issues throughout the project has been challenging. Despite concentrated and systematic efforts through different partners in the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, including a specific focus on Responsible Research and Innovation practices, gender and diversity reporting was limited in most experiments, particularly regarding the monthly field notes taken by local partners. This challenge resulted in issues being underrepresented or not discussed at all and therefore invisible for the analysis process.

4.2. Policy recommendations: ways in which gender and intersectional diversity matter for the Green Transition

1. **Mainstream an intersectional understanding of gender from the beginning of Green Deal strategies, to help unpack the complex issues of the green transition**

The EU Commission has the tools to appreciate intersectional understandings of the green transition, e.g., the anti-racism action plan, the Roma strategy, LGBTI strategy, disability strategy. The EU's future gender equality strategies should not be siloed and instead develop broader definitions of gender, in order to capture the complexities of experience rather than binary understandings of 'men' or 'women'.

2. **Provide accessible and targeted training for those doing social research and project implementation on Green Deal topics**

Accessible, local training regarding gender and intersectionality need to be made available to those who are engaging in local work on the green transition – be that research or project implementation. Training should include how to develop inclusive and gender-sensitive communication methods, considering local languages or dialects, as well as non-verbal communication. When training is developed, the engagement of local actors would establish better embedment to local cultural norms.

3. **Adopt focused reporting, including gender indicators, in all Green Deal topics**

Reporting for all EU projects on green transition topics (including EU Horizon projects) should adopt focused reporting using gender indicators. For example, something similar to the OECD Gender Marker could be enacted, which ensures that gender impacts are continuously monitored throughout financial and project reporting.

4. **Collect holistic gender-disaggregated data on the Green Transition, including extensive research on the impact of gender stereotypes**

a. The continued lack of gender-disaggregated data makes it harder to develop tailored policies for the green transition. Future policymaking should be based on gender-disaggregated data by expanding the reach of the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) to focus on more than issues of representation, but also economic and social realities of the green transition specifically.

b. Additionally, when focus on gender occurs in research projects, it mostly focuses on gender representation rather than on the more complex issues of social stereotypes, gender norms, and biases. A more sensory and participatory approach, enabling people to contribute experiences and norms through non-verbal or non-traditional communication, such as through images, videos and storytelling can help capture richer and more informative insights for understanding the lived realities of the green transition.

5. **Acknowledge reproductive labour as a key pillar of the green transition**

Reproductive labour remains a highly gendered sphere of life, with women carrying a larger load in regard to the management of home, and of expectations for care, homeliness and comfort. This realm is often obscured by household level data and cannot be left behind in the green transition. The EU should address care and the household as a key pillar of the transition, by collecting data on the complexity of household consumption, including how

everyday life decisions and practices are allocated and negotiated, paying attention to issues such as mental load, invisible household labour and time availability.

6. Use Green Deal Communications to challenge stereotypes

The EU has a key role to play in challenging stereotypes of masculinised and feminised practices through green technologies and infrastructures. The EU's communication should challenge stereotypical expectations, such as of women being (better or sole) carers and expand social norms about all genders entering non-gender-traditional professional domains such as construction or textiles/fashion. Additionally, recognition and support of more tacit and practical types of knowledge and know-how need to be explored and given value within the EU's Research agenda (such as the Horizon programme).

5. Conclusions

This report is one of five reports on SSH priority themes, highlighting empirical insights on how Gender and Intersectional Diversity were designed-in and facilitated in the 24 social experiments of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

Our analysis illustrates the challenge of translating gender as a matter of representation of women and men in the interactions of the social experiments. At the same time, other dimensions, such as gender dynamics, gender norms, stereotypes and conventions, gendered roles and practices (in professional or everyday life), gendered communication and gendered spaces can easily be left out or misunderstood, leading to them not being appropriately integrated (in the design and facilitation of the experiments) and reported. Further to the understandings of gender, the concept of intersectionality was used in the analysis as a lens to expose the structural dimensions of systems of power and how they interact. However, due to the scope and depth of the data, intersectionality was mostly utilised for identifying categories of intersecting issues, such as social and cultural background and the ways in which they interacted with gender. The intersections that came up more frequently in the data than others include age, professional expertise or experience and disability.

The report presented some positive learning points, regarding gender & intersectional diversity, from the implementation of the experiments. These include examples about the process and methods used for building inclusive learning, therefore generating safe spaces for people to express themselves, share experiences and co-create knowledge. The report also highlighted how the experience of girls and women in specific contexts, through practices such as cycling, home renovation and the process of transitioning to a new energy landscape helped promote new roles practices and leadership for women in the community. Additionally, the report highlighted how gendered knowledge can pass down through intergenerational interactions, through for example mother-daughter or teacher-student relationships.

It has been unclear on how the social experiments affected the gendered ways that people take action on issues of the green transition after participating in the social experiments, however, there were indications that women, overall, had higher representation in the experiment interactions across all 24 social experiments, and higher interest in issues of the green transition.

The report finally highlighted some shortfalls regarding the gendering of certain professional spaces and roles. Examples include the feminised fashion/ textile industry and food industry, and the masculinised construction industry and farming, as well as the challenges that these present when people try to break through, and gain trust and recognition of their expertise in a non-stereotypical gender role.

Some important implications for governance and policy include the need for a more explicit integration of gender and intersectionality in Green Deal strategies and projects, in addition to accessible and targeted training for those involved. This training should be based on a holistic feminist approach that addresses structural issues, their barriers, and how to overcome them. This would lead to a movement away from labelling groups as merely 'vulnerable'. Furthermore, local and EU governance structures should address and design ways to capture the complexity of invisible (physical and mental) labour that still overburdens women (or that is socially expected of them), such as care and household management. These two areas are important pillars for the

green transition of households and communities. Finally, it is important to support the facilitation of gender appropriate and gender transformative communication. This can help change prevailing stereotypes and social expectations, such as gendered expectations for care and homeliness. It can also allow for the recognition of different kinds of expertise and knowledge, such as tacit and practical know-how, making them more visible and allowing them to contribute to technical, scientific and other types of explicit knowledge that this green transition requires.

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Appendix A1. Data collection processes

Table A1.1. Social experiments profiles

#	Priority area (thematic stream)	Approach	Target group	Place of social experiment	Local partner organisation	Context (rural/urban)*
1	Clean Energy	Community visioning	Policymakers, businesses, local communities	Granada, Spain	Local authority (Diputación de Granada)	mix
				Bełchatów, Poland	NGO (Polish Green Network)	mix
				Jaywick, UK	Local authority (Essex County Council)	rural
				Ærø, Marstal, Denmark	NGO (Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators)	rural
2	Circular Economy	Local accelerator hubs	Local businesses, academics, authorities, and NGOs	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Santo Tirso)	urban
				Val-de-Marne, France	NGO (Val de Marne en Transition)	urban
				Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus	National authority (Cyprus Organization for Standardization)	mix
				Ljubljana, Slovenia	Local authority (Technology Park Ljubljana)	urban
3	Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks on energy renovation and eco-home-tours	Under-represented and marginalised groups and renovation professionals (40-60% women)	Zaragoza, Spain	NGO (ECODES Zaragoza)	urban
				Nógrád County, Hungary	NGO (Habitat for Humanity Hungary)	rural
				Vilnius, Lithuania	Local authority (Let's Renovate the City Vilnius)	urban
				Louisburgh, Mayo County, Ireland	Regional authority (Mayo County Council Louisburgh)	rural
4	Sustainable Mobility	School mobility labs	Per experiment 30 young people (aged 10-16) and 5 to 10 stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and school administrators	Braga, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Braga)	urban
				Galway, Ireland	NGO (Am Meitheal Rothar Ireland)	urban
				Panevėžys, Lithuania	NGO (ECAT Lithuania)	urban
				Sofia, Bulgaria	NGO (Sofia Development Association Bulgaria)	urban
5	Sustainable Food	Local food Assemblies	Young people aged 18-35 years	Stockholm, Sweden	NGO (REFORMATEN)	urban
				Cella Monte, Italy	NGO (ASFODELO)	rural
				Košice, Slovakia	NGO (Klíma ťa potrebuje)	mix
				Wageningen, Netherlands	NGO (Gemeente Wageningen)	mix
6	Preserving Biodiversity	Study Circles	Diverse group of 10-15 adults per Study Circle (ensure diversity in age, gender, occupation and social vulnerability)	Tolmin, Slovenia	NGO (Posoški razvojni center)	rural
				Amaroussion, Greece	Local authority (Municipality of Amaroussion)	urban
				Kilfinane, Ireland	NGO (Ballyhoura Development CLG)	rural
				Stockholm, Sweden	Local authority (Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm)	urban

*Note: Rural/urban is based on [European Commission \(2014\), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation.](#)

Table A1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by	Comment / Description
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants ³	SGD consortium members (WP4)	Interviews were conducted by local partners with a variety of participants in social experiments (respecting representative selection criteria), then transcribed and analysed by consortium members. The analysis was guided by specific codes relevant for SSH priority themes - defined ahead - and organized per social experiment stream (Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Efficient Renovation, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, Preserving Biodiversity), resulting in six codebooks. Per stream, 10 interviews of approx. 30-60 min. were conducted (240 in total).
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners	At the end of each month, local partners filled in a monthly survey about the ongoing experiments that was prepared by the consortium partners, directed already towards SSH priority themes. (288 surveys in total).
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members	Consortium members met with the local partners of each experiment monthly and took note of the developments and progress in the social experiments. For each experiment, the 12th meeting note summarizes all meetings of the past 12 months and reflects on the whole process.
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners	Local partners were given an extensive reflection survey, that included a narrative /qualitative part in which they were asked to reflect and describe the journey of their experiments (24 surveys and 24 experiment journey files (reflections by local partners).
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members	The team of WP 6 - Impact evaluation and RRI integration conducted interviews with respective consortium members of each experiment's stream. (6 interviews in total).
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners	Shared Green Deal's call for application to host social experiments in the six Green Deal priorities areas received 344 applications in which the candidate organizations (NGO's, association, local authorities (municipalities) detailed how they would conduct the experiments and assure qualitative criteria (i.e. inclusive approach) and commit to previous training provided by the project.
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members	Project partners held webinars on each Green Deal priority topic, describing the respective social experiment journeys (https://sharedgreendeal.eu/multimedia/playlist-local-actions-shared-green-deal).

³ Due to the nature of the qualitative data, openly sharing full datasets would risk compromising participant anonymity. However, anonymised interview transcripts for #DS1 and for each of the six experiment streams are available and can be accessed at the Zenodo platform, community SHARED GREEN DEAL. For **Circular Economy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Circular Economy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387249>; for **Clean Energy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Clean Energy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15274546>; for **Efficient Renovations**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Efficient Renovations [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076033>; for **Sustainable Food**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Food [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387236>; for **Sustainable Mobility**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Mobility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15325897>; for **Preserving Biodiversity**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Preserving Biodiversity [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076035>.

Table A1.3. The different steps of the secondary analysis for the Gender and Diversity theme

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	Step 6
Develop the analysis plan and create mapping tables and timeline	Collate the data and go through the difference sources (deductively) to map where research Qs can be found	Divide the data sources amongst partners and perform inductive thematisation	Internal Workshop amongst the Gender & Diversity partners to discuss preliminary findings	WP4 codebooks arrive-AAU to go through them WECF-to check webinars for triangulation	Final themes for the report Writing plan Final report

Table A1.4. The timeline of the Gender and Diversity analysis tasks

2024			2025						
Octo	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July
Step 2	Step 2 & Analysis draft complete GA meeting presentation	Step 3	Step 4- and begin to look at draft deliverable report	Step 5	Step 5/6- Cross theme workshop	Step 6	First draft of 5.1- contribution for G & I	Revisions based on feed-back from WP leaders	

Appendix A2. Coding and data analysis

Table A2.1. Gender codebook

Name	Description	Files	References
1.0 good practices	This code collects gender-aware/ sensitive practice as well as feminist methodologies described in the experiments. It also collects good practice examples of how gender was incorporated in the design / planning of the social experiment	34	67
2.0 problematic statements about gender	This code is used to identify perspectives, perceptions and narratives that can be considered problematic (from feminist point of view) e.g. misinterpretation of gender or gender equality concepts. Also includes problematic statements or implicit notions regarding social norms or stereotypes that might be problematic regarding intersectional diversity.	21	60
3.0 background & context	This code involves any contextual information relevant to gender issues both directly relevant to the experiment and regarding relevant contextual issues that might be useful for the analysis (e.g. examples of diversity issues, or gender norms in general but not necessarily regarding the experiment itself). Also includes general background regarding the social experiment that might be useful to consider in the analysis	50	160
4.1 gender norms & stereotypes	Includes mentions of stereotypical gendered social norms in the given context, specifically when engaging in the experiment, but also outside of it. It includes stereotypical perceptions of how everyday life should be organised such as general expectations of behaviours for different genders, at individual and collective level	17	121
trust		1	7
4.2 gendered roles, practices & performances	Includes mentions of (socially constructed) gendered roles in the experiment and in everyday life in general, but when referring to how these affect the performance of practices related to the experiment. Things to include: gendered professions/roles, gendered performances of certain practices in the context of the experiment	34	146
4.3 gendered expertise & interests	Includes references to association of any kind of expertise (professional, layperson, lived /tacit experiences etc.) with gender. Also includes mentions of gendered interests (i.e interests shaped by prevailing gender/ social norms), as well as associated assumptions about these	16	114
community action		2	8
recommendations for training		1	5
4.4 lack of gender issues	Mentions of gender not being an issue, mentions of non-observed gender difference in gender norms/ stereotypes, roles, practices and expertise	18	43

Name	Description	Files	References
5.1 gender representation & participation in experiment	Includes actual gender representation as we all perceived/ assumed gender representation in the experiment. This includes gender-related issues regarding participation in the experiment (e.g. unable to attend due to care responsibilities or other gendered responsibility or issue). Also includes mentions about trying to achieve gender balance in the experiments	64	184
5.2 gender dynamics	Gendered differences reported regarding interactions between participants, or local partners or others in the experiment, incl. dominant voices/ representations etc.	46	123
recommendations for gender dynamics & participation		2	6
5.3 lack of gender representation or dynamics	Mentions of the lack of gender representation or dynamics	32	50
6.1 Intersectionality-background	The intersection of gender with different kinds of background issues (e.g. social, cultural, economic etc.)	28	56
6.2 Intersectionality-age	Includes the intersection of gender with age (e.g. older men/women and representation, intergenerational issues etc.)	30	106
6.3 Intersectionality-education and prof. expertise	Includes the intersection of gender with mentions regarding education/literacy issues, as well as mentions of gender intersecting with professional roles / practices	17	69
6.4 Intersectionality-disability	Intersections of gender with physical and / or mental disability or impairment	10	56
6.5 lack of intersectionality	Includes mentions of the lack of intersectional issues/ approaches and understandings in the context of the experiment	9	21
6.6 other intersectionality issues	Anything not fitting in the previous categories	30	55
care duties and parenting	Includes mentions regarding issues relevant to intersections with parenting or other care duties, that can become an issue for inequality, e.g. care duties preventing participants to attend the experiment, or mentions of single parenting or other which can affect the participants and their social conduct	3	21
decision making	Mentions of inclusion or exclusion in decision-making processes that affect participants	2	20

Name	Description	Files	References
Embodied, tacit experience & expertise	Mentions of specific experiences or expertise which refer to the embodied, tacit & lived experiences (or lack of) related to unequal or not fair inclusion or participation. Examples include, how experiences of comfort are intersecting with gender, age and background, or how taste or other subjective aspects of everyday life intersect with socio-cultural background, gender etc.	5	24
employment & labour	Mentions of employment / occupation/ work commitments/ any other form of paid or unpaid labour (or lack of) related inequalities, e.g. unemployment or preventing people from participating in the experiment or other interaction, household labour, invisible mental labour etc.	4	29
income	Mentions of income inequalities and/or injustices intersecting with people's engagement in the experiment or related activity and/or affecting their experience, includes poverty or being in threat of poverty	2	5
language & communication	Mentions of language related issues intersecting with other issues and affecting people's engagement in the experiment or related activity and/or affecting their experience. Language refers not only to the spoken words and expressions, but also to unspoken, embodied communications including sounds, signs, and other gestures or expressions which hold meaning in the specific socio-cultural context	4	7
ownership		2	2
7.1 gender & vulnerability, justice & inequality	Mentions regarding issues gender & vulnerability, social inclusion, justice etc.	19	39
7.2 gender & societal challenges post COVID	Mentions of intersections of gender with issues related to COVID and its affects (e.g. social isolation)	6	7
7.3 gender & governance agendas, conventions & framings	Mentions of intersections of gender with issues / instances of governance (e.g. local community governances, issues of leadership	6	12
7.4 gender & geogr. differences & evolutions across time	Mentions of intersections of gender with geographic differences (e.g. Local customs/ contexts/ norms)	9	13
8. Gendered communication & language	Mentions of gendered communication, gendered language and terminologies used to address issues and people and that determined by gendered social norms	26	37
9. Gendered spaces	Mentions of how space and place can be gendered, including both physical spaces/ places as well as conceptual spaces (e.g. professional space, community space etc.)	3	15

Table. A2.2. Table relating the research questions to each data source

RQs/ Data sources	Applications (DS#1)	Field notes (DS#2)	Webinar (DS#5)	RRI surveys (DS#3)	RRI interviews (DS#3)	Codebooks (DS#4)
RQ1	Applications include data about local partners' expectations on engagement/ participation with few examples of gender differentiated participation	The local partner responses to the gender-related question provide information about the existence (or lack) of differentiated dynamics of engagement. However, most responses refer rather to the absence of gender dynamics or to other criteria than gender (intergenerational differences).	The webinar has been used only for triangulating the findings of other sources	Some indications although mostly indirect mentions to gendered dynamics. Intersections with the Vulnerability (e.g. social exclusion) and Societal Challenges themes	Mentions to dynamics during the experiment interactions, and within the research team Intersections with Vulnerability	Rich evidence across all experiments
RQ2	Applications do not provide relevant data for RQ2	The field notes do not provide relevant data to RQ2 as the information provided by the local partners do not reflect on the ways that participants are translating the experiment learnings into practical action	As above	Limited evidence, as action is not traced in this source, but only small mentions	Examples of practices (sayings and doings) indicating gendered performances that show how people undertake the experiment issues in the daily life	Some mentions, but not very extended evidence about how people translate concepts into action. This question was more challenging since the participants were not necessarily followed much outside the experiments' interactions
RQ3	Some (very limited data) about local partners expectations on potential motivations to participate.	Few references to how different genders have interest or are motivated by different aspects of the experiment (e.g. in biodiversity).	As above	Very limited evidence	Limited, as these were interviews with consortium partners with some but not many references to participants' interests and engagement with the themes of the experiments	Good source for gendered interests, although stereotypes and norms make this question more challenging to answer

RQs/ Data sources	Applications (DS#1)	Field notes (DS#2)	Webinar (DS#5)	RRI surveys (DS#3)	RRI interviews (DS#3)	Codebooks (DS#4)
RQ4	Some information on how the experiment would address gaps in participation or access, (e.g. Claddagh, Galway-Mobility and Belchatów -Clean Energy) Mentions to specific target within the renovation experiment	The field notes can be used to highlight, for example, the cases in which the local partners mention the implementation of gender responsive methodologies for facilitation or prompted discussions about gender-specific barriers	As above	Good evidence for tracking local partners' reflections on the successful points and useful for mapping the 'invisibility' of gender (as defined in our introduction) overall		Good evidence for finding the challenges of integrating an intersectional approach to the experiments, and good source for identifying good practices
RQ5	The most prominent aspect could be the experiment with gender-related objectives (in Mobility and clean energy)	Very limited information relevant for the research question. As with the application, one approach could be focusing on the clean energy experiment in Poland as it has a strong focus on the transition from a (male-dominated) mining region and how the transition can be seen as an opportunity to change traditional dynamics.	As above	This is a relevant source for the RQ, but is challenging to understand the social norms in each context	Very limited or non-relevant	Some evidence on stereotypically gendered practices across the experiments, but more limited evidence of how practices can be affected in the long term
RQ6	Applications include a few references to genders over/under-representation in specific fields.	Very limited data relevant to the research question	As above	This question can be traced from answers about inclusion and participation in the experiments	Small explicit evidence but useful source for developing insights the consortium partners' understandings of gender and intersectional diversity	Rich source for developing reflections and learning points based on insights about the ways that gender was encountered in the social experiments, through the participants' experience

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